

Analysis of heat stress in classrooms of different school building types

Type of school building of the Prefabricated Period Typ „Dresden Atrium“: 108. Grundschule in Dresden (Sachsen)

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Published on 18.09.2025

Approach and goals

Climate change is leading to higher temperatures and more frequent heat waves, which is particularly dangerous for children under the age of 12. School classes are often in classrooms for more than six hours a day, which affects health, well-being and learning performance at high room temperatures. Since pupils can hardly influence the temperatures, they are particularly at risk. In addition, the school building stock is usually not designed for increasingly hot summers and tends to overheat anyway due to the large window areas of classrooms. The joint project KlimaKonform II therefore investigated how high the heat load is in classrooms of different school building types in Saxony, Saxony-Anhalt and Thuringia and which heat adaptation measures are particularly effective.

This study uses a combined approach to analyze heat stress and thermal comfort in seven schools. These include three schools from the Wilhelminian period (1870–1918) in Plauen, Dresden and Gera, two prefabricated schools (1970–1990) in Zeitz and Dresden, a school from the post-war period (1952) in Dresden and a newly built school, also in Dresden. The comparison can be used to determine which building types are particularly susceptible to extreme heat stress.

This profile reports on the results on heat stress and thermal comfort in the school building type of prefabricated construction, based on the 108th primary school in Dresden (Saxony).

The analysis follows the process shown in the diagram below and consists of several steps:

- **Step a: Selection of representative school buildings**
- **Step B: Temperature measurements in classrooms**
Continuous measurement of classroom and outdoor temperatures from June to the end of September 2024 in two classrooms per school.
- **Step C: Survey of pupils and teachers on the perceived heat stress**

At the same time, pupils and their teachers in the two classrooms per school were asked how they felt about the indoor climate in summer. The survey makes it possible to record temperature-dependent well-being.

- **Step D: Effectiveness analysis of heat adaptation via thermal building simulation**

In addition, detailed 3D models of the examined classrooms were created for thermal building simulations. In this way, the effectiveness of different adaptation measures can be tested and compared in simulations.

Linking these steps (a to d) ensures that both objectively measured and subjectively perceived aspects of thermal comfort are taken into account.

This profile focuses mainly on structural-technical and behavioural adaptation to reduce heat stress in classrooms. The equally relevant school organisational measures (location of the summer holiday period, shortened lessons, switching to cooler classrooms) and schoolyard design aspects are not the subject of this profile.

108. Grundschule in Dresden (Sachsen)

a General information about the school

Description

The 108th primary school in Dresden (Saxony) is a typical example of Dresden's atrium prefabricated concrete construction method with windows on two sides of the room. The classrooms have external sun protection on the south side and internal glare protection. The large window fronts of the classrooms are oriented to the southeast.

Source: Google Earth, 07/2022

Source: Christoph Schünemann, 06/2024

General information

Type of school	Primary school
Design	Prefabricated building (Dresden type)
Address	Hepkestraße 28 01309 Dresden
Status of the renovation	Retrofitted
Grade levels taken into account	3rd and 4th grade

Classroom South-East Façade (Room 015)

Window details	Floor space	50,4 m²
	Orientation of the windows	South-East
	Window glazing	Older double glazing
	Shading	Exterior venetian blinds (south-facing windows)
	Ventilation	Window ventilation
	Exterior wall	Prefabricated reinforced concrete components with light insulation
	Interior wall	Reinforced concrete
	Ceiling	Prefabricated reinforced concrete components

Classroom South-East Façade (Room 207)

Window details	Grundfläche	50,4 m²
	Orientation of the windows	South-East
	Window glazing	Older double glazing
	Shading	Exterior blinds (south-facing windows)
	Ventilation	Window ventilation
	Exterior wall	Prefabricated reinforced concrete components with light insulation
	Interior wall	Reinforced concrete
	Ceiling	Reinforced concrete (prefabricated construction)

Source: Christoph Schünemann, 06/2024

108. Grundschule in Dresden (Sachsen)

b Survey of pupils on heat stress

General Information

On four different days, students from two classrooms were asked about their perception of heat stress. Room 015 is used by 3rd grade students, while Room 207 is used by 4th grade students. On a typical summer day (survey date: August 27, 2024), 21 people in room 015 and 19 people in room 207 participated. On the hot survey day (August 20, 2024), there were 20 students in each room.

Source: Christoph Schünemann, 06/2024

Summer Day (27.08.2024)

Room 015 at 11:40		Room 207 at 11:10	
Exterior	23,1 °C	Exterior	23,1 °C
Interior	25,1 °C	Interior	25,0 °C

The values in the pie chart show the number of responses in each class on the day of the survey.

● Cold ● Cool ● OK ● Warm ● Hot ● No information

Pie charts to compare the temperatures perceived by the students in both classrooms: on a typical summer day (left) and on a hot day (right).

● Very well ● Well ● OK ● Unwell ● Very unwell ● no information

Both rooms were rated similarly in terms of temperature perception both on a typical summer day and on a hot day. The majority of the students found the room temperature pleasant on a summer day and on a hot day.

● Not tired ● Something tired ● Very tired ● No information

The reported feeling of fatigue was similar in both rooms on both summer days and hot days.

Hot day (14.08.2024)

Room 015 at 11:30		Room 207 at 11:30	
Exterior	30,0 °C	Exterior	30,0 °C
Interior	27,6 °C	Interior	29,6 °C

Measures taken during the survey

Room 015	Room 207
Cross ventilation through open door and window	Ventilation through open window
External sun protection used	External sun protection used

Room 015	Room 207
Cross ventilation through open door and window	Ventilation through open window
External sun protection used	External sun protection used

Conclusion

The perceived heat stress in the classroom was significantly more critical in both rooms on a hot day than on a summer day, which is also reflected in the high indoor temperatures of up to 30 °C on a hot day at the time of the survey. This is expressed in the perception of temperature and well-being. Without the existing external sun protection, much more critical survey results on the perceived heat stress would be expected. However, the feeling of fatigue hardly seems to be temperature-dependent.

108. Grundschule in Dresden (Sachsen)

c Temperature measurements and simulations in the classroom

Outdoor temperature measurement with KLIPS sensor

- Outside temperature
- School operations

The outside temperature was recorded with a [KLIPS](#) temperature sensor in the street space at a distance of 250 m. The outside temperature from 5.8 to 11.9.2024 is shown here. This study period was heavily heat-laden and had 14 hot days (maximum outside temperature above 30 °C), 1 tropical night (minimum outside temperature at night above 20 °C) and 11 warm nights (minimum outside temperature at night above 18 °C).

Classroom interior measurements

- School operations
- Temperature in the room 015
- Room temperature 207
- Outside temperature

Between August 5 and September 11, 2024, only room 207 exceeded the critical room temperature of 30 °C four times. However, both rooms frequently exceeded the comfort temperature of 26 °C, with room 207 doing this more often than room 015. The maximum temperature for room 207 was over 30 °C, while for room 161 it is almost 29 °C. Due to its location under the roof, room 207 is much more heat-loaded. Room 015 is also cooled by the basement.

Thermal building simulations of the current state (classroom 207)

The comparison of the simulated room temperature curve with the measured room temperature curve in the actual state is satisfactory using the local climate and the assumption that in the period from 8:00 to 14:00 (weekdays) three windows are open on each side if the outside temperature is less than the room temperature. In addition, two additional windows are open every 10 minutes for fresh air (regardless of the room temperature).

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d Effectiveness of heat adaptation measures and recommendations

Effectiveness of adaptation measures to reduce heat stress

Simulations of measures for heat adaptation

The bar diagram shows the overtemperature degree hours (ÜTG) for different simulation variants of both classrooms. The ÜTG are an indication of how many hours and how much the comfort temperature of 26 °C per year (Kh/a) is exceeded in the classroom. While v0 represents the reference (actual state) of the room, the other variants show the following differences:

In its current state, the ÜTG in room 207 is significantly higher than in room 015.

Automatic window ventilation day and night (v4) has the strongest effect on reducing heat stress in both rooms.

Solar control glazing (V3) also significantly reduces the ÜTG in both classrooms.

Temperature curves of classroom 207 for different variants

The above-mentioned findings are also clear in the diagram of the temperature curve for room 207 on the left.

Recommendations

The measurements, surveys, simulations and comparison with the classrooms of other school buildings lead to the following assessment and recommendation regarding the reduction of heat stress:

Classroom 207 is significantly more heat-stressed than room 015 on the ground floor due to the lower shading due to the lack of trees in front of the building and due to the higher heat input from the sun-drenched tar roof. For example, the attic classroom 207 has room temperatures of up to 30 °C, which, according to simulations, would rise to over 33 °C without the subsequently installed slat shading and would entail an even higher heat load. It must therefore be ensured that teachers use sun protection as an effective heat adaptation measure as permanently as possible on hot days.

Furthermore, we recommend checking whether automatic night-time window ventilation is feasible, especially for the classrooms on the upper floors, as this significantly reduces the heat load once again. With regard to climate protection, we urgently recommend an energy-efficient renovation of the school due to the low wall thickness. Care should be taken to ensure glazing with a low total energy transmittance and to preserve the external shading.

General recommendations, derived from the comparison of the school buildings examined, can be found here:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19651356>